

GENETIC DIVERSITY AND INSECTICIDAL POTENTIAL OF *BACILLUS THURINGIENSIS* STRAINS ISOLATED FROM UZBEKISTAN: PREVALENCE OF CRY1, CRY2, AND VIP3A GENES

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Abstract. *In this study, we investigated the presence and diversity of insecticidal cry-type genes in native 68 Bacillus thuringiensis (Bt) strains isolated from Uzbekistan. To determine the presence of lepidopteran-active insecticide genes, cry1, cry2, and vip3A gene families were selected and analyzed through PCR-based screening. The total genomic DNA was extracted and used as a template for PCR amplification. The results demonstrated that cry1-type genes were the most prevalent, present in 88.23% of the native 68 Bt strains, followed by cry2 genes in 61.76% and vip3A genes in 17.64% of the strains. These findings were consistent with other studies, indicating a strong presence of cry1 genes across different Bt strains. This research contributes to the understanding of the genetic diversity of Bt strains in Uzbekistan and highlights the importance of further investigations into the cloning, characterization, and expression of these unique insecticidal genes. Such efforts could provide new opportunities for integrated pest management in sustainable agriculture, enhancing the development of novel biopesticides for effective pest control.*

Keywords: *Bacillus thuringiensis, cry-vip3 genes, genetic diversity, biopesticides, PCR, primers.*

Introduction

The commonplace Gram-positive, rod-shaped, and sporulating bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) has been isolated globally from a wide range of environments, including soil, water, dead insects, silt, dust from silos, leaves from deciduous trees, various conifers, and insectivorous mammals, as well as from severely necrotic human tissues [1-4]. Each strain may be particularly active against pests that are lepidopteran, dipteran, coleopteran, or hymenopteran, as well as other invertebrates like mites and nematodes, depending on the levels of Cry, Cyt, and Vip proteins [5-7]. There are 14 subfamilies (cry1A-N) within the cry1 family, and between them are 275 cry genes. Most of the cry1 genes are functional in preventing lepidopteran pests from spreading. This family's cry1b and cry1I genes are effective against coleopteran pests as well [8]. With roughly 82 genes, the cry2 family is ranked second and mostly targets lepidopteran or dipteran pests. During the vegetative growth phase, species of *B. thuringiensis* also produce vegetative insecticidal proteins, or VIPs [9]. Binary toxins Vip1 and Vip2 exhibit insecticidal action against pests of the Hemiptera and Coleoptera [10], while Vip3 proteins exhibit insecticidal activity against pests of the Lepidoptera [11, 12]. The toxicity potential of these Vip3 proteins against vulnerable insects is comparable to that of Cry proteins.

To improve resistance to lepidopteran genes, seven anti-lepidopteran cry and vip genes-cry1Ab, cry1A105, cry1Ac, cry1F, cry2Ab, cry2Ae, and vip3A-have been employed. The most utilized genes to create lepidopteran-resistant crops are cry1Ab, cry1F, and cry1Ac; these genes have been included into 61, 51, and 32 genetically modified varieties, respectively [13].

In Uzbekistan, the cotton bollworm mostly affects the Fergana, Andijan, Namangan, and Tashkent regions, causing significant harm to cotton farms. comparatively less harm in other areas. However, it seriously damaged the Kashkadarya region's Nishon and Mirishkor districts in 2020. It seriously damages tomatoes, corn, eggplant, peas, and legumes in addition to cotton. Should no control measures be implemented, 20–30% of the crop will sustain damage. 60–80% damage if neglected. Damage from average hard impact years can reach 30%.

Materials and methods

Bacterial strains, chemicals and oligonucleotide primers

The Bt were isolated from Uzbekistan. “GenPak® PCR Core” was used for PCR amplifications, oligonucleotide primers were synthesized by IDT ([Integrated DNA Technologies](#)). To determine active lepidopteran active insecticide genes, cry1, cry2, and vip3A gene families were selected.

PCR-based cry gene screening in local Bt strains

The total genomic DNA of 68 Bt strains were extracted according to standard protocols “Marmur procedure” [14]. The total DNA pattern of all Bt strains were analyzed on agarose gel. Genomic DNA isolated from Bt strains were used as template for the PCR amplification. Each 20 ul reaction mixture contained 50 ng of genomic DNA of Bt strain, 10 ul dilution, 0.4 ul of forward and reverse primers each, 8.2 ul double distilled water. The amplifications were conducted with the thermal cycler (BioRad, USA). The PCR was performed for 35 cycles as follows: 94°C for 3 min, primer annealing for 40 s and 72°C for 1 min., the final extension was performed for 10 min at 72°C. Electrophoresis was carried out at 140 V for 25 min in TAE electrophoresis buffer. Data analysis was done using GelDoc (BioRad).

Results and discussion

Cry gene detection through PCR in regional Bt strains

The amplification of PCR fragments of the expected size using different primer pairs (Table 1) confirmed the presence of the mentioned insecticide-type genes in the 68 Bt strains. Since all the strains carried cry1-type genes, they were the most prevalent (88.23%) among native 68 Bt strains, followed by cry2 (61.76%) and vip3A (17.64%) (Fig.1). Using the same screening primers, agarose gel electrophoresis revealed both nonspecific amplification and a particular partial cry gene amplicon, which were also seen in numerous published research findings.

Table 1 Oligonucleotide primers utilized for the screening of partial insecticide-type genes for Lepidopteran insects

No	Primers name	Sequence (5' 3') →	Gene name	Product size bp	References
1	Lep1A Lep1B	CCGGTGCTGGATTTGTGTTA AATCCCGTATTGTACCAGCG	cry1Aa, cry1Ab, cry1Ac	490	[15]
2	cry2F cry2R	GTTATTCTTAATGCAGATGAATGGG CGGATAAAATAATCTGGGAAATAGT	cry2	701	[16]

3	vip3AF vip3AR	ATGAACAAGAATAATACTAAA GCGGCCGCTTACTTAATAGAGAC	vip3A	2300	[17]
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Fig. 1 Agarose gel electrophoresis of **a.** PCR amplification of partial cry 1A gene from 68 Bt strains. **b.** PCR amplification of partial cry2 gene from Bt strains. **c.** PCR amplification of Vip3A gene from Bt strains. M-100 bp DNA ladder (a and b figures); M-1kb DNA ladder (c figure).

Jain et al. [18] examined the frequency of insecticide-type genes in eight Bt strains (IS1–IS8) and found that, as determined by PCR, cry1 type genes were the most prevalent in the native isolates because all the strains carried them. These were followed by vip3A (87.5%), cry2 (75%), cry9 (62%), cry3 (50%), cry11 (37.5%), cry7–8 (37.5%), cry5, 12, 14, 21 (25%), cyt1 (25%), cry4 (12.5%), and cyt2 (12.5%). The diversity of cry genes from various soil types and climatic environments was reported by Patel et al. [19]. They also found that while cry3 and cry13 genes were absent from isolates of non-agricultural samples, cry1, cry2, cry3, 7, 8, cry4, cry5, 12, 14, 21, cry11, cry13, and cyt1 genes were found to be present in Bt. Parallel to this, Salekjalali et al. [20] used PCR to identify isolates carrying distinct cry-type genes and discovered that 47% of the

strains amplified using the cry1 primer, 29% with the cry3 primer, and 13% with the cry4 primer. The cry1 gene is the most prevalent of the investigated cry-type genes in these isolates (83.33%), according to Salama et al. [21]. Cry1 gene subfamilies (cry1B and cry1C) had percentages of 38.88 and 77.77%, respectively, behind the cry1 gene. The cry2A gene was present in the examined isolates, however not all the isolates (61.76%) tested positive for the cry2 gene. Of the examined isolates, only 61.76% and 17.64%, respectively, had cry2 and vip3A genes. A presence of all three genes family in Bt1fo, Bt10, Bt13, Bt16, Bt19, Bt24, Bt99, Bt amb1; and cry1 and cry2 genes family in Bt1, Bt2fo, Bt3, Bt3fo, Bt4, Bt6, Bt7, Bt7fo, Bt12, Bt19fo, Btx20, Bt21, Btx24, Bt27, Btx27, Btx28, Bt28, Bt29, Bt31, Bt32, Btx33, Bt38, Bt39, Bt77, Bt100, Bt106, Bt mth, Bt var.thur, Bt26 strains; cry2 and vip3A genes family in Bt35, Bt98 strains, and only vip3A gene in Bt105 strain; only cry2 gene family in Bt43, Bt80, Bt103 strains; in addition to these, only cry1 family genes in Bt6fo, Bt10fo, Bt12fo, Bt13fo, Bt17fo, Btx18, Bt18fo, Bt20fo, Btx30, Btx45, Bt45, Bt57, Bt76, Bt84, Bt93, Bt94, Bt101, Bt102, Bt104, Bt300, Bt1-4, Bt2-3, Bt amd strains and absence of all three genes family in Bt30 and Bt72 strains were determined by PCR results. Cry gene detection has been substantially enhanced using PCR; nevertheless, this technique is primarily restricted to members of already identified gene families and necessitates many primers. The current study's findings imply that the native Bt isolates are diverse. Additional research on the cloning and characterization and expression of those unique insecticide genes from these fresh isolates of Bt will be beneficial and present fresh prospects for integrated pest management in sustainable agriculture in Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

This study highlights the predominance of cry1-type genes in native 68 Bt strains, with a significant majority (88.23%) of the strains carrying these genes. The detection of cry2 and vip3A genes, though less frequent, indicates additional insecticidal potential within the strains. Overall, these findings enhance our understanding of the genetic diversity of Bt strains and their potential utility in developing effective biopesticides.

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